

Parallel versus Twisted Pentacenes: Conformational Impact on Singlet Fission

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ABSTRACT

We placed two pentacene chromophores at the termini of a diacetylene linker to investigate the impact of excitation wavelength, conformational flexibility and vibronic coupling on singlet fission. Photo-excitation of the low-energy absorption results in a superposed mixture of states, which transform on an ultrafast time-scale into a spin-correlated and vibronically coupled/hot delocalized triplet pair $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$. Regardless of temperature, the lifetime for $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$ is less than 2 ps. In contrast, photo-excitation of the high-energy absorption results in the formation of $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$ lasting 1.0 ps, which then decays at room temperature within 4 ps *via* triplet-triplet annihilation. Lowering the temperature enables $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$ to delocalize and vibronically decouple, in turn affording $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{loc}}$. In addition, our results suggest that the quasi-free rotation at the diacetylene spacer may lead to twisted conformations with very low SF quantum yields, highlighting the need of controlling this structural aspect in the design of new singlet fission active molecules.

TOC GRAPHICS

The use of triplet excited states (T_1) in up/down-converting solar energy processes in single-junction solar cells has proven a useful tool to maximize the use of the solar spectrum, introducing also ways to overcome the Shockley-Queisser efficiency limit.^{1,2} In this context, multiple exciton generation in semiconductor materials and singlet fission (SF) in molecular materials are promising candidates to maximize the efficiency of solar cells.

In SF, interactions between two neighboring SF-chromophores enable the down-conversion of one high-energy singlet excited (S_1) state into two low-energy triplet excited (T_1) states, residing on different chromophores.³⁻⁶ A key thermodynamic requirement that SF-materials must fulfill is to exhibit at least a twice as high energy of (S_1) to (T_1): $E(S_1) \geq 2 \times E(T_1)$.⁷⁻¹⁰ Here, polyacenes, and pentacene in particular, stand out as SF-chromophores due to their favorable (S_1) and (T_1) energies.¹¹⁻¹⁶ Additionally, close proximity between SF-chromophores should be ensured to govern inter-chromophore coupling.^{11,17-22} In this respect, the use of covalently bonded dimers exhibiting intramolecular SF (iSF) provides an appealing approach for coupling control. In these SF-dimers, the nature of the molecular spacer is of paramount importance as it enables exert specific effects on SF,¹⁶ tune SF-dynamics and optimize SF-yields, therefore imposing structural constraints for SF materials.²²⁻²⁸

Regarding the mechanism of SF, it is still a matter of controversy. Still, two main pathways are usually considered. On one hand is the direct SF-mechanism, lacking any intermediate states during the transition from the singlet excited state (S_1S_0) to the singlet-correlated triplet pair $^1(T_1T_1)$. On the other hand, the mediated SF-mechanism is considered in which charge transfer (CT) states act as mediators for the population of $^1(T_1T_1)$.^{17,26,29-32}

To get insight into the correlation between structure and mechanism in SF, in this work we used a linear diacetylene spacer to rigidly place two pentacene chromophores in close proximity

(LiDi³³), to probe the impact excitation wavelength, conformational flexibility, and vibronic coupling have on the SF mechanism.³⁴ To this end, we characterized the iSF mechanism using transient absorption spectroscopic methods and quantum dynamics simulations employing parallel (**pLiDi**) and twisted (**tLiDi**) conformer model systems (see Figure 1a and SI for details).

Figure 1. (a) Molecular structures of the parallel (**pLiDi**) and twisted (**tLiDi**) conformers of the linear pentacene-dimer **LiDi** (detailed description on the synthesis is given in the SI). Steady-state absorption spectra (b) of **TIBS** (black), **LiMo** (red), and **LiDi** (blue) in MeTHF,

together with the calculated absorption spectra of **pLiDi** (c) and **tLiDi** (d). The calculated spectra have been obtained by a Fourier-transform of the product of the autocorrelation function and convoluted with an exponential damping function with 40 meV full width at half maximum (see SI). The plots have been scaled for better visibility.

A detailed discussion on the steady-state absorption and fluorescence of **LiDi** and its differences to the references (**TIBS** and **LiMo** – Figure 1a) in different solvents and at cryogenic temperatures is given in the SI (Figures 1, S5-S13 and Table S1). In short, the results point towards the presence of parallel (**pLiDi**) and twisted non parallel (**tLiDi**) conformations, which either strongly coupled or decoupled pentacenes, respectively. The origin of the two main absorption features at 677 and 737 nm (Figure 1b) and their respective connection to **pLiDi** and **tLiDi** was supported by simulated absorption spectra using quantum dynamical methods (Figure 1c,d).³⁵

Time-resolved measurements were carried out to investigate the deactivation kinetics of **TIBS**, **LiMo**, and **LiDi**. Results and discussions on **TIBS** and **LiMo** are given in the SI (Figures S15-S25 and Table S2). Excitation wavelengths of 633 and 750 nm were selected to excite into the high- and low-energy transitions of **LiDi**, respectively. All of the femtosecond transient absorption spectra (fsTAS) were chirp-corrected during the target analysis of their raw data. In MeTHF, photo-excitation of **LiDi** at 750 nm results in the immediate observation of maxima at 460, 500, 552, 600, 885, and 970 nm as well as GSB at 680 nm. The raw data are best fit by a one-species kinetic model with a lifetime of 1.7 ps, by which the ground state is quantitatively regenerated. The overall shape differs from that of (S_1) from **LiMo** and **TIBS** with, for example, a lack of the maximum in the NIR between 1300-1400 nm, usually very prominent in

pentacenes. But, it also differs from that of (T_1). While a peak at 470 nm is present, as found for (T_1) in **LiMo** (Figures S20-S23), it lacks the more prominent peak at 500 nm (Figure S37). Limited by our instrumental time resolution of <200 fs, we cannot resolve its formation. This is where theoretical calculations become essential. They cover the excited state dynamics up to 600 fs and reveal that several states, which we collectively call (M), are involved in populating the spin-correlated triplet pair, in particular when the parallel **pLiDi** conformation is photo-excited – *vide infra*. In light of its short-lived nature, we postulate a vibronically coupled/hot and delocalized triplet pair $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$.³⁶ Lowering the temperature to 80 K overall led to bathochromic shifts, sharper maxima in the visible, and a drop in intensity at 980 nm in the NIR. This is in sound agreement with the steady-state measurements, in which similar bathochromic shifts were noted (Figure S10). The lifetime remained very short, indicating the same deactivation kinetic as in room temperature (Figures 2 and S34–S36).

Photo-excitation of **LiDi** at 633 nm results in a different picture. At room temperature, the instantaneous formation of maxima at 460, 495, 980, and 1300 nm are noted in MeTHF (Figure S29a,b). GSB evolves at 680 and 740 nm, which corresponds to the high-energy absorption of twisted and low-energy absorption of parallel conformers, respectively. In terms of target analysis, the first observable species combines spectral features of different states, which relate to (M) – *vide supra*. Unlike experiments with photo-excitation at 750 nm, we deconvoluted (M) within 1 ps and follow its transition to the spin-correlated triplet pair $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$. In particular, maxima at 465, 497, 945, and 1200 nm are accompanied by GSB at 674 nm. The GSB of (M) appears broad, while we find a narrow GSB for $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$, the same as for $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 750$ nm, thus linking them (Figure S37). The overall differences in peak position and lifetime might stem from the initial excitation of different high-energy states due to varying excitation wavelengths. From

strong inter-pentacene interactions, on one hand, and fast formation dynamics, on the other hand, we conclude that fast intramolecular SF is taking place. This is opposed to the slow and inefficient **LiMo** decay via ISC. Relative to (T_1) of **LiMo**, the spectral differences of $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$, namely the absence of the broad feature near 450 nm and a broader GSB, are attributed to vibronic coupling (Figure S37). The electronic ground-state is regenerated via triplet-triplet annihilation from $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$ within 4 ps at room temperature (Table S2).^{37,38}

Next, we conducted measurements of **LiDi** with a photo-excitation of 633 nm at different temperatures. At 80 K, maxima evolve at 460, 500, 906, 1040, and 1310 nm, next to GSB at 700, 728, and 760 nm (Figures 2 and S29c,d). The GSB is a perfect mirror image of the features recorded in the absorption spectrum (Figure S9) with contributions from parallel **pLiDi** and twisted **tLiDi** conformers. From single wavelength analyses at 700 nm, three lifetimes of 3.3, 12.9, and 81.5 ps are found as opposed to two lifetimes derived from room temperature. In contrast, at 760 nm only one lifetime is obtained. This is in perfect agreement with the photo-excitation experiments at 750 nm. When decreasing the temperature stepwise, the lifetimes of both (M) and $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$ increase (Table S2), concurrent with sharpening of $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$. Starting at around 220 K, a three-species kinetic model gave better results (Figure S30), with a now biphasic decay of $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$. Spectroscopically, both $^1(T_1T_1)$ states feature the same fingerprints, although subtle differences are discernable. First, GSB is blue-shifted from 688 to 684 nm upon transforming from the first to the second triplet pair. Second, the triplet excited-state fingerprints, namely 471 and 504 nm, are better resolved/sharper in the latter.

In a previous work,³⁹ we found a similar biphasic behavior and rationalized the existence of two unique triplet pairs on the basis of the following argument. At 80 K, the two triplet excited states are vibronically decoupled and each localized on a pentacene moiety. Increasing the temperature

to 295 K, leads to the population of $^1(T_1T_1)$ that is delocalized and vibronically coupled. For **LiDi**, formation of the two triplet pairs is facilitated through strong interactions leading to an initially delocalized and vibronically coupled/hot $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$, which later relaxes into a localized and vibronically decoupled $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{loc}}$ at lower temperatures (Figures 2 and S29–S31, Table S2). A general mechanistic view of the deactivation mechanism of **LiDi** is illustrated in Figure 3.⁴⁰

Figure 2. Differential fsTAS ($E = 400$ nJ) of **LiDi** in MeTHF at 80 K. Left side: Lower panel shows the spectra with $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 633$ nm and upper panel shows the respective chirp-corrected and normalized species associated spectra (SAS) of the mixed state (M) (black), the delocalized and vibronically coupled/hot $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$ (red), and the localized and vibronically decoupled $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{loc}}$ (blue) as obtained by target analysis, using the kinetic model shown in Figure 3. Right side: Lower panels shows the spectra with $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 750$ nm and upper panel shows the respective chirp-

corrected and normalized species associated spectra (SAS) of the delocalized and vibronically coupled/hot state ${}^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$ (black) as obtained by target analysis, using the kinetic model shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. General mechanistic schemes illustrating (a) the deactivation pathways of **LiDi** with all observed transitions of the respective twisted and parallel conformation with an excitation wavelength at 633 nm at room (295 K) and cryogenic (< 220 K) temperatures and (b) with an excitation wavelength of 750 nm.

To support our experimental findings and shed light on the short-time dynamics of the intramolecular SF process in **LiDi**, we carried out quantum dynamics simulations explicitly

incorporating the coupling to the laser field (see eq. S1) up to 600 fs. Figure 4 shows the wavelength dependent SF-dynamics for **LiDi** after photo-excitation at either 659 or 717 nm, corresponding to the two low-lying vibrational bands of the parallel conformer **pLiDi** (see Figure 1 and SI for details). Our results for both excitations consistent with a mediated SF mechanism where CT states $|^1(\text{AC})\rangle$ and $|^1(\text{CA})\rangle$ are not significantly populated, yet our model also suggest a non-negligible contribution from the direct SF-channel (see SI).^{7,41} In detail, light absorption prompts the population of $|^1(\Phi_+)\rangle$, the linear combination of two diabatic locally excited $|^1(\text{S}_1\text{S}_0)\rangle$ and $|^1(\text{S}_0\text{S}_1)\rangle$, leading to a value of $\sim 11\%$ at ~ 200 fs when **pLiDi** is photo-excited at 659 nm and a slightly larger value of $\sim 16\%$ with photo-excitation at 717 nm. Next, a decrease of the $|^1(\Phi_+)\rangle$ population begins to emerge and this decrease goes hand-in-hand with the rise of $|^1(\text{T}_1\text{T}_1)\rangle$. $|^1(\text{T}_1\text{T}_1)\rangle$ reaches a maximum of $\sim 15\%$ at 500 fs upon 659 nm photo-excitation and $\sim 16\%$ at ~ 250 fs upon 717 nm photo-excitation. From that point, the population of $|^1(\text{T}_1\text{T}_1)\rangle$ depends on the excitation wavelength. Specifically, low energy excitation generated $|^1(\text{T}_1\text{T}_1)\rangle$ continues to decay beyond 250 fs and reaches a value of $\sim 12\%$ at the end of the simulation time. In contrast, upon photo-excitation at 659 nm, the decay of $|^1(\text{T}_1\text{T}_1)\rangle$ is much slower and plateaus with an average value of $\sim 15\%$ over the time range of 350-600 fs. Therefore, iSF in **pLiDi** is excitation wavelength dependent across the considered short time range. In addition, the simultaneous population of several excited states (see Figure 4 and SI), which all co-exist throughout the early timescales of SF, can rationalize the mixed spectroscopic features of (M) seen in the experiments.

To assess the impact of quasi-free rotation about the diacetylene linker on SF, we have also analyzed the SF-dynamics for **tLiDi**, a model of a twisted **LiDi** conformer (see Figure 4 and SI for details). Similarities, but also differences evolved. All states show much lower populations

for **tLiDi**, regardless of the photo-excitation wavelength. Apart from these differences, the SF-dynamics of **tLiDi** are subject to a similar wavelength dependence as summarized for **pLiDi** (*vide supra*). Thus, upon photo-excitation the evolution of the $|^1(\Phi_+)\rangle$ population decays quickly with excitation at 717 nm, but much slower with excitation at 659 nm, exhibiting a higher population than $|^1(T_1T_1)\rangle$ during the considered simulation time.

Figure 4. Simulated time evolution of the population of the diabatic states involved in the intramolecular SF process of **pLiDi** (top) and **tLiDi** (bottom) conformers after photoexcitation at 717 nm (left) and 659 nm (right). The laser field intensity was chosen to achieve a $\sim 20\%$ population of the $|^1(\Phi_+)\rangle$ state of **pLiDi** excited at 717 nm (see SI for details).

To summarize, we have synthesized **LiDi**, an acetylene linked pentacene dimer, to assess the impact that conformational flexibility, excitation wavelength and vibronic coupling have on the

intramolecular SF-mechanism. Steady-state absorption measurements reveal vibrational splitting, inferring the existence of at least two types of conformers, in which the pentacene moieties are placed either parallel or twisted with respect to each other. Using time-resolved transient absorption spectroscopy we have analyzed the low and high-energy transitions of **LiDi**. Photo-excitation of the low-energy transitions identifies a superposed mixture of states, which transform into a single observable species, namely a delocalized vibronically coupled/hot triplet pair $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$ with a short lifetime (<2 ps). Photo-excitation of the high-energy transitions of **LiDi**, on the other hand, results in the observation of a superposed mixture of states and its transformation into $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$ within 1.0 ps. This state decays to the ground state within 4 ps via triplet-triplet annihilation. Lowering the temperature allows the identification of two different correlated triplet pair excited states, with different spectroscopic features. We relate these states to the delocalized $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$ and to a localized and vibronically decoupled $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{loc}}$ state, respectively. These results are supported by theoretical calculations that are consistent with an iSF dominated by the mediated-like mechanism and excitation-wavelength dependent on short time scales (ca. <10 ps). In addition, theory suggests that the quasi-free rotation at the diacetylene spacer exhibited by **LiDi** may easily lead to twisted conformations with very low SF quantum yields. Altogether, our results emphasize the necessity of controlling conformational flexibility in the design of new SF-active materials.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. (I) Listing of the general experimental methods; (II) text and schemes describing the synthetic routes; (III) ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra; (IV) text, figures and tables illustrating results from ground state, excited state, and time-resolved transient absorption spectroscopy; (V) text, figures and tables describing the theoretical details.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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- (35) The sum of the calculated **pLiDi** and **tLiDi** spectra fail to perfectly match the **LiDi** spectrum since many non-parallel conformations co-exist at any given temperature. Furthermore the calculated spectrum of **pLiDi** is a perfect parallel orientation, whereas the spectra for **LiDi** at 80 K still feature a mixture of frozen conformers, explaining the discrepancy. Still some characteristics of **pLiDi**, that is, the different ratios of the absorption peaks are clearly present in **LiDi** at 80 K.
- (36) Similar results were gathered in the other solvents (Figures S32-S34a,b, Table S2).
- (37) We note an additional species with maxima at 449 and 501 nm and GSB at 674 nm and a lifetime of 1.3 ns, strongly resembling (S_1) of **LiMo** but being very low in intensity (<1%). A reasonable rationale is based on the free rotation along the bis-acetylene spacer, allowing conformers unsuitable for SF and undergoing slow and inefficient ISC to yield (S_0T_1). A long-lived fluorescent component is also seen in time-correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) measurements, confirming the parallel existence of a fluorescent (S_1) not undergoing SF (Figure S13, Table S1).
- (38) Short TTA lifetimes on the same order of magnitude have already been reported in the past. In this case it is related to strong vibronic coupling and inter-pentacene interactions in **LiDi**. While the other solvents at room temperature induced some differences in the spectral shape of (M) and $^1(T_1T_1)_{\text{deloc}}$, in particular the GSB and NIR, likely caused by slight changes of the electronic states/coupling of the pentacene moieties, the same overall behavior could be observed (Figures S27, S28, and S38 Table S2).
- (39) Basel, B. S.; Hetzer, C.; Zirzmeier, J.; Thiel, D.; Guldi, R.; Hampel, F.; Kahnt, A.; Clark, T.; Guldi, D. M.; Tykwinski, R. R. Davydov Splitting and Singlet Fission in Excitonically

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- (40) Again some differences between the spectral shapes of the species could be noted when cooling down, caused by changes of the electronic states/coupling of the pentacene moieties (Figure S38 and S39).
- (41) Berkelbach, T. C.; Hybertsen, M. S.; Reichman, D. R. Microscopic Theory of Singlet Exciton Fission. II. Application to Pentacene Dimers and the Role of Superexchange. *J. Chem. Phys.* **2013**, *138*, 114103.